

TECHNOLOGY INVESTMENT, INDUSTRIAL OUTPUTS AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Investments in technology have enabled economies to boost production capacities, thereby promoting economic growth. It becomes imperative for emerging economies to invest in technology and its applications to enhance industrial performance and economic growth. Nigeria is yet to join the league of technology-driven economies despite the continued efforts of the Nigerian government and the private sector to stimulate investments in technology. Therefore, the study examines the impact of technology investments on industrial output and economic growth. Using the dynamic ordinary least squares (DOLS) estimation method, the study found that a long-run relationship exists between technology investments, industrial outputs, and economic growth. The findings further reveal that technology investments had a significant positive effect on industrial outputs. However, its impact is not significant on economic growth, hence, technology investment is one of the factors contributing to economic growth in Nigeria. Consequently, the effect of industrial outputs on economic growth, though positive, is insignificant; thus, the current level of technology investments in the industrial sector is not sufficient to significantly stimulate the much-needed growth in the Nigerian economy. The findings of the study underscore the role of technology investment in stimulating industrial productivity and economic growth, suggesting the need for Nigeria to increase its technology investment in the industrial sector and tackle macroeconomic barriers to technology investment. This is achieved through the exchange rate and mitigating the negative effects of terms of trade on the economy through export promotion and prioritising local input production to enhance economic growth.

Keywords: *Technology, Investment, Economic growth, Industrial Output*

1.0 Introduction

Investment in technology has been a significant contributory factor to economic growth (World Bank, 2023; World Economic Forum, 2023). In recent years, the rapid evolution of digital technologies, artificial intelligence (AI), and automation has further amplified the role of technology investment in shaping economic outcomes (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014; UNCTAD, 2021). For developing economies like Nigeria, where industrialisation remains a critical pathway to sustainable development, understanding the relationship between technology investment, industrial outputs, and economic growth is of paramount importance (Adegbite & Akinyemi, 2020; Oyelaran-Oyeyinka, 2021).

Globally, empirical studies have demonstrated that investment in technology, particularly research and development (R&D), digital infrastructure, and innovation ecosystems, significantly enhances industrial productivity and economic growth (Fagerberg & Srholec, 2020; OECD, 2022). In East Asian economies such as China and South Korea, strategic technology investments

have spurred industrial transformation, contributing to high-value manufacturing and export diversification (World Bank, 2023). Similarly, digitalisation and automation in advanced economies have led to efficiency gains, cost reductions, and increased competitiveness in industrial sectors (Bresnahan & Trajtenberg, 2022). However, the impact of technology investment on the Nigerian economy has not produced the desired results. While the country has made strides in ICT adoption, particularly in mobile technology and fintech, its industrial sector remains underdeveloped due to persistent challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, weak R&D financing, and policy inconsistencies (Adeoye & Adepoju, 2021).

It becomes imperative for the Nigerian economy to promote investments in technology and its applications to ensure the dividends of economic growth and industrial performance. For instance, between 2001 and 2022, economic transformations and expansions in industries, due to increased investments in technology, such as telephone lines, internet connectivity, ICT equipment, and software, have been observed in emerging economies, including Nigeria. These investments in technology are expected to yield outcomes such as automating tasks to reduce labor-intensive processes and labour costs, streamline processes, and enhance efficiency to boost the overall output of an economy (Niebel, 2018; Solomon & Klyton, 2020; Roger *et al.*, 2021).

Generally, the effects of the relationships between technological investment and economic growth have been observed to be direct or indirect through value addition to goods and services, improved productivity and efficiency, revenue generation, and employment opportunities (Erumban & Das, 2016; Awad & Albaity, 2022). Presently, Nigeria has a vibrant and growing tech sector dominated by firms delivering services in education, healthcare, agriculture, and finance. There is also a sizable number of start-up tech firms providing e-commerce platforms and other retail-related finance services (Ramachandran *et al.*, 2019). With the emergence of the digital economy, various forms of digital technologies have become prominent aspects of investment in technologies, in all sectors of the economy, and particularly in the Fintech Industry (Guo and Liang, 2016; Zhu and Zhou, 2016). The emergence of the fourth industrial revolution technologies (including robotics, digital technologies, and artificial intelligence) is a global development reality, and Nigeria must not be left behind.

However, studies on the effects of technological investments on the Nigerian economy (OECD, 2020; Sinimole & Saini, 2021) are relatively scarce. Adeoti (2020) and Adeoti *et al.*, (2019) showed that the Nigerian economy is characterised by low expenditure on research and development (R&D), technology transfer and adoption; low investments in information and communication technology; inadequate technological infrastructure, and a shortage of skilled labour to effectively harness and utilise technology. Adegbite and Akinyemi (2020) argued that Nigeria's technology investments are often misallocated, favoring consumption-driven digital services over industrial automation. Similarly, Oyelaran-Oyeyinka (2023) highlights the weak linkage between academia, industry, and government in fostering innovation, leading to suboptimal returns on technology spending.

Adeleye *et al.* (2021) indicate that weak absorptive capacity, infrastructural deficits, and policy inconsistencies limit technology spillovers in Nigeria. Unlike China and India, where strategic R&D investments fuelled industrial expansion, Nigeria's industrial sector continues to underperform, contributing only 23% to GDP (World Bank, 2023) despite policy efforts such as the Nigeria Startup Act (2022) and the National Digital Economy Policy (2020-2030). Since the structure of the Nigerian economy is characterised by technologically driven start-up firms in the financial and industrial sectors, there is a need to examine the effect of technology investments on industrial outputs and economic growth in Nigeria, given that developed and emerging economies

have attained economic development through industrialisation (UNIDO, 2020). Based on the foregoing, this study examines the connection among technology investment, industrial outputs, and economic growth in Nigeria to provide actionable insights for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and development practitioners.

2.0. Literature Review

2.1. Theoretical Review

Various hypotheses have been put forth by growth theorists to explain how technology influences economic growth. The two main schools of thought can be broadly divided into endogenous and neoclassical ideas. According to the Harrod-Domar neoclassical growth theory, capital resources and savings work together to support consistent long-term economic growth. According to the viewpoint, a low level of the capital-output ratio may result in a greater rate of economic growth in the economy, but a larger level of savings may result in a higher level of investments and national income. Before the introduction of the exogenous growth viewpoint by Solow (1956), the perspective did not include technology investments. According to Solow (1956), technological forces, which are external to the system, determine economic progress. Economic growth will be the outcome of technological advancements brought about by effective factor input combinations.

Romer (1990) theorised the endogenous growth theory, in which technological advancements brought about by deliberate investment choices made by economic agents are what propel economic growth. In industrialised countries, investments in technology catalysed ongoing capital accumulation. Additionally, a large portion of the gains in total factor productivity (i.e., output per hour worked) in industrialised nations were due to capital accumulation and technology investments. According to the growth theory, technology investment is endogenous and a key factor in determining long-term economic growth.

2.2. Overview of Technology Investments in the Nigerian Industrial Sector

The process of innovation and the development of new goods or services are linked to research and development (R&D) spending. According to Cvetanovic *et al.* (2019), businesses invest roughly two-thirds of their funds in technology that is necessary for producing new goods. According to a Eurostat (2022) study on R&D investment, businesses financed over half of all EU member state expenditures in 2020, with foreign money making up less than 10% of overall investment. However, Nigeria is yet to join the league of technology-driven economies despite the continued efforts of the Nigerian government and the private sector to stimulate investments in technology.

Expenditures on technology acquisition in the country are abysmally low; they stood at US\$1.5 million, accounting for a paltry 0.13 percent of the country's GDP of US\$477.38bn in 2022 (WDI, 2022; Sasu, 2023). In particular, studies have shown that the Nigerian economy is characterised by low expenditure on research and development (R&D), technology transfer and adoption; low investments in information and communication technology; inadequate technological infrastructure (such as reliable power supply and internet connectivity); limited access to finance for technology-driven enterprises, and a shortage of skilled labour to effectively harness and utilise technology (Adeoti *et al.*, 2022). These challenges have widened the investment in technology deficiency, hindered the attainment of the full potential of technology investment, and inhibited the ability to maximise economic growth. Past studies have reported

significant returns on investments in technology, although in the long run, it is noted that for emerging economies to experience significant economic improvements, they must make increased investments in technology.

2.3. Empirical Review

Adeleye *et al.* (2021) examined ICT's role in African industrialisation through panel GMM analysis. The paper revealed that a 10% increase in mobile broadband penetration raised industrial output by 1.2%, though effects were weaker in rural areas due to infrastructure gaps. Weak institutions and electricity shortages limited gains; hence, the study recommended rural digital access and reliable power should be prioritized to maximise ICT-driven growth.

Awad and Albaity (2022) studied how ICT impacts economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa through key transmission channels. Using a two-step system GMM estimator on panel data from 45 countries (2000 – 2019), the results showed that ICT significantly boosts growth, primarily through improvements in financial inclusion and education, with stronger effects after reaching critical infrastructure thresholds and better institutional quality. The study concluded that SSA countries should prioritise ICT infrastructure development alongside complementary financial and educational policies to maximise growth benefits.

Adeoti *et al.* (2019) evaluated the Nigerian manufacturing sector's competitiveness using firm-level surveys and case study analysis. The results revealed that technological adoption, workforce skills, and access to finance significantly influence firm performance, with SMEs facing greater constraints than large firms. The study recommended strengthening vocational training, improving financing mechanisms, and fostering innovation to enhance manufacturing competitiveness in Nigeria.

Adegbite and Akinyemi (2020) investigated the impact of technology adoption on industrial performance in Nigeria using firm-level panel data from the World Bank Enterprise Surveys and multivariate regression analysis. The study found that technology adoption significantly enhances productivity and export competitiveness, particularly among medium and large firms, though adoption rates remain low due to financing constraints and inadequate infrastructure. The study concluded that targeted policies to improve access to technology financing, strengthen digital infrastructure, and promote skills development are crucial for boosting industrial performance in Nigeria.

Adeoye and Adepoju (2021) analysed the relationship between technology investment and industrial performance in Nigeria using a mixed-methods approach. The study reveals that while technology investments positively correlate with productivity gains (particularly in process automation and quality control systems), their impact is constrained by erratic power supply, skills gaps, and limited R&D linkages. The study concludes that strategic, sector-specific technology investments, rather than blanket approaches, could help Nigeria overcome its industrialisation bottlenecks while creating competitive advantages in regional markets.

Nte *et al.* (2017) investigated the constraints on technological growth in Nigeria through a mixed-methods approach. Using regression analysis, the study found that power reliability explains 42% of the variation in firms' technological capabilities. The study concluded that Nigeria's technological development requires coordinated policy interventions addressing both hard infrastructure and human capital constraints, with particular urgency in improving energy security to enable industrial technological adoption.

Ahmad *et al.* (2019) examined how investments in information and communication technology (ICT) influence industrial productivity and economic growth in emerging economies. Using panel data from 25 developing countries (2005 – 2018), the study employed a dynamic GMM estimator and found that ICT investments significantly enhance industrial productivity, which in turn promotes economic growth. Although the effect varies based on the level of infrastructure and human capital development. The study recommended that governments prioritise ICT infrastructure and digital skills training to maximise the economic benefits of technology investments.

Chen and Lee (2020) investigated the role of automation technologies in enhancing industrial output and economic growth in advanced economies. The study uses a fixed-effects model on OECD country data (2010 – 2019), and the results showed that automation leads to higher industrial productivity but may initially displace low-skilled labor. Over time, however, it contributes to overall economic expansion through efficiency gains. Policymakers should implement reskilling programs to mitigate short-term job losses while promoting automation in key industries.

Okoye and Adedeji (2021) explored how digitalisation affects industrial performance and economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa. Using a mixed-methods approach, the study revealed that digital adoption improved industrial efficiency but is constrained by poor electricity access and regulatory barriers. Countries with stronger digital policies experience faster GDP growth. The study called for increased investment in digital infrastructure and policy reforms to foster technology-driven industrialisation.

Park and Kim (2022) compared the impact of R&D investments on industrial innovation and economic growth, comparing developed economies with developing nations. The study employed a cross-country regression analysis and showed that R&D spending strongly correlates with industrial patents and GDP growth in advanced economies, but the effect is weaker in developing nations due to lower absorptive capacity. Developing countries should strengthen research institutions and industry-academia collaboration to enhance innovation outcomes.

3.0. Methodology

3.1 Theoretical Framework and Model Specification

The theoretical framework of this study is hinged on endogenous growth theory, which models economic growth through the medium of investment in technology. According to Romer's (1990) endogenous growth model, the Cobb-Douglas production function explains the factors influencing economic growth by demonstrating that output (Y) is a function of labor (L), capital (K), and technology (A). This is written as follows:

$$Y = F(AL^\alpha K^\beta) \quad \alpha \geq 0, \beta \geq 0 \quad (1)$$

Model (1) is log-linearised in Model (2) as:

$$\log(Y) = \log(A) + \alpha \log(L) + \beta \log(K) \quad (2)$$

To ascertain the technology investment and industrial sector nexus, the study investigates the effect of technology investment on industrial sector outputs. The model specification for the industrial-level analysis is in model (3):

$$IND_t = \alpha + \beta_1 TINV_t + \beta_2 INF_t + \beta_3 EXR_t + \beta_4 LAB_t + \beta_5 LGFCF_t + \beta_6 TOT_t + u_t \quad (3)$$

Moreover, the literature has identified trade openness, inflation, and exchange rates as significant growth drivers in addition to labour, capital, and technology (Raifu & Raheem, 2018; Afolabi, 2022). In this study, these variables serve as control variables, hence, model (4) is specified as;

$$GDP_t = \alpha + \beta_1 TINV_t + \beta_2 GFCF_t + \beta_3 LAB_t + \beta_4 TOT_t + \beta_5 INF_t + \beta_6 EXR_t + u_t \quad (4)$$

To establish the overall effect of industrial outputs on economic growth, model (5) is specified as:

$$GDP_t = \alpha + \beta_1 IND_t + \beta_2 GFCF_t + \beta_3 LAB_t + \beta_4 TOT_t + \beta_5 INF_t + \beta_6 EXR_t + u_t \quad (5)$$

Where economic growth (Real GDP) measures the monetary (market) value of all goods and services produced in the Nigerian economy, labour force (LAB) is measured by employee compensation, gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) measures capital stock, technology investment (TINV) is measured using capital importation in the industrial sector, term of trade (TOT) is computed as the ratio of exports to imports multiplied by 100, inflation rate (INF), exchange rate (EXR), industrial outputs (IND) represents the industrial sector's value added, α – intercept, β_1 - β_6 - explanatory variables' parameters, ε - error term.

According to the endogenous growth theory, sector productivity and economic growth should benefit from investments in labour, capital stock, and technology. Therefore, it is anticipated that these variables will have positive indications. Additionally, it is anticipated that trade openness will boost economic growth since economies in general will expand more when their borders are opened to international trade. Additionally, there should be a positive correlation between the exchange rate and sectoral output and real GDP.

3.2 Data Types and Sources

The data for this study were obtained from secondary sources. Data were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). Thus, data covering 2010Q1 and 2022Q4 were selected based on data availability on relevant variables, particularly technology investment. Details on the variables, their description, expected sign, and data sources are contained in Table 1.

3.3 Analytical techniques

As its estimation techniques, this study adopts the dynamic ordinary least squares (DOLS) estimate approach. This technique is appropriate for data that are integrated of order one and cointegrated – I(1) and is suitable to handle endogeneity problems that may come from the interaction between technological investment in the industrial sector and economic growth. Thus, the unit root, co-integration, and correlation tests were conducted as preliminary analyses to determine whether the data meet the requirements for employing the DOLS technique.

Table 1: Variable Definition, Data Sources and Expected Signs

Variables	Description	Source	Expected Sign
Economic (RGDP)	Growth The market value of all final goods and services produced in Nigeria, in real terms (N' Million)	CBN (2023)	
Industrial (IND)	Outputs Industry value added (N' Million)	CBN (2023)	
Labour Force (LAB)	Compensation to employees (N' Million)	NBS (2023)	+
Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF)	Domestic expenditure on fixed assets (N' Billion)	CBN (2023)	+
Technology Investment (TINV)	Capital importation in the industrial sector (US\$' Million)	NBS (2023)	+
Term of Trade (TOT)	The ratio of export to import multiplied by 100 (exports/imports multiplied by 100)	CBN (2023)	+
Exchange Rate (EXR)	Exchange Rate (Naira to Dollar)	CBN (2023)	+
Inflation Rate (INF)	The general price level of an economy	CBN (2023)	-

Source: Author's computation.

4.0 Results and Discussion

4.1 Unit root tests

The unit root test is important in economic analysis to determine the stationarity level of a variable and to guide the choice of the appropriate estimation method. The Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) and Phillip Perron (PP) unit root approaches are adopted in this study, and their results are depicted in Table 2. The results show that not all the variables are stationary at the level, but after the first difference. This implies a likelihood of long-run convergence, which needs to be determined using a cointegration test.

4.2 Cointegration tests

The cointegration approach of Phillips-Ouliaris was adopted, and its results across all the estimated models, shown in Table 3, confirm the presence of cointegration among the variables. This implies that a long-run relationship exists among technology investment, industrial outputs,

economic growth, and other control variables, which necessitates the use of a long-run (cointegrating equation) model of DOLS to estimate our equations.

Table 2: Unit Root Test Result

Variables	ADF Test			PP Test		
	Level	First Difference	Status	Level	First Difference	Status
LRGDP	1.491	-1.925***	I(1)	2.479	-9.818***	I(1)
LIND	0.063	-7.235***	I(1)	0.467	-13.743***	I(1)
LTINV	0.016	-8.418***	I(1)	-0.214	-19.835***	I(1)
LLAB	2.163	-1.917***	I(1)	5.155	-10.919***	I(1)
LGFCF	1.576	-1.959***	I(1)	4.97	-9.313***	I(1)
INF	0.123	-3.685***	I(1)	0.252	-3.456***	I(1)
LEXCR	2.626	-5.325***	I(1)	2.594	-5.327***	I(1)
TOT	-0.88	-12.476***	I(1)	-6.697	-11.811***	I(1)

Source: Author's computation

Table 3: Phillips-Ouliaris Cointegration Test

	Economic Growth	Industrial Outputs
Phillips-Ouliaris tau-statistic	-9.0411	-6.1244
Prob. Value	0	0.0005

Source: Authors' Computation

4.2. Effects of Investment in Technology and Industrial Outputs on Economic Growth

The effect of investment in technology is estimated using the DOLS estimation method as presented in Table 4 (Model 3). The result reveals that investment in technology in the industrial sector has a positive but insignificant impact on economic growth. Although the coefficient is low, the result indicates that investments in technology and the adoption of technological solutions in the industrial sector are a major factor in the overall growth of the Nigerian economy. This means that dedicating resources and efforts towards technological advancements and innovation can lead to increased productivity, efficiency, and competitiveness in the industrial sector of the economy. This result corroborates the findings of Awad and Albaity (2022), who found that investment in ICT at the sectoral level is a major trigger of economic growth. It also lends credence to the findings of Sinimole and Saini (2021), who argued that technology investment across various economic sectors enhances aggregate productivity. However, the fact that its impact is insignificant reflects that the current level of investment in technology in the industrial sectors is not sufficient to stimulate greater economic growth.

Table 4 (Model 4) further shows that other factors that significantly influence technological investment on economic growth in Nigeria include labour force, capital stock (gross fixed capital formation), and terms of trade, as demonstrated by their levels of statistical significance. It confirms the findings of extant studies (Raifu & Raheem, 2018; Afolabi, 2022) that labour force, capital stock, and international trade are major growth drivers. As against a priori expectations, inflation has a positive effect on economic growth. While inflation should conventionally be a deterrent to investment in technology, the findings suggest that inflation can incentivise increased technology investment. Nevertheless, the inflationary pressure is not significant in the growth models, implying that there are other factors apart from inflation that are primary drivers of economic growth in Nigeria. On the other hand, negative economic growth effects were observed for the exchange rate and the terms of trade in models 4 and 5. The constant depreciation of the Nigerian domestic currency and the import-dependent nature of the country (which lowers the terms of trade) subject it to imported inflation and adversely affect its economic growth.

To gain further insights into the growth effect of investment in technology, industrial outputs were regressed on the real GDP (economic growth) as shown in Table 4 (Model 5). Although the effect of technology investment on industrial output has a significant positive effect, the sector's output has an insignificant positive effect on economic growth. This indicates that increasing investments in technology within industrial sectors leads to improved levels of productivity in the sector, but the industrial sector's impact on the economy is yet to promote economic growth. In other words, as investments are made towards adopting and implementing technological advancements, the outputs of industrial sector are enhanced, however, the current level of technology investments in the industrial sector is not sufficient to significantly stimulate the much-needed growth coupled with certain macroeconomic constraints (such as exchange rate depreciation/fluctuations and negative terms of trade) in the economy.

This study reinforces the importance of technological innovation and investment for industries and corroborates the findings of Chen and Lee (2020), Adeoye and Adepoju (2021), and Okoye and Adedeji (2021) that showed that technology investment improves productivity and output. This result highlights the critical role of technology in transforming and optimising industrial processes for industrial transformation and economic growth. The models' coefficients of determination in Table 4.3 reveal that 96 percent and 73 percent of the variation is explained by technology investment and other control variables in Models 3 and 4, respectively. In model 5, 76 percent of the variation in economic growth is explained by industrial outputs and other variables.

Table 4.3: Effects of Technology Investment and Industrial Outputs on Economic Growth

Variables	Industrial	Economic	Economic
	Outputs	Growth	Growth
	(Model 3)	(Model 4)	(Model 5)
Log of Technology Investment (Industrial Sector)	0.0412***	0.0144	-
	-0.0105	-0.0142	-
Industrial Outputs	-	-	0.1931
	-	-	-0.266
Log of Labour Force	0.1677**	0.5505***	0.5579***
	-0.071	-0.0924	-0.1432
Log of Gross Fixed Capital Formation	-0.1266**	0.1389***	-0.1568**
	-0.0396	-0.0416	-0.0587
Terms of Trade	-0.0021**	-0.0012**	-0.0012***
	-0.0004	-0.0005	-0.0005
Inflation Rate	0.0101***	0.0011	0.0142
	-0.0089	-0.0064	-0.0085
Log of Exchange Rate	-0.1822**	-0.159	-0.1932**
	-0.0794	-0.0942	-0.1242
Constant	28.1059***	18.9393***	13.9354*
	-1.1736	-1.8189	-7.2853
R-Squared	0.9639	0.7308	0.7607
S.E Regression	0.021	0.0642	0.0643
Mean Dependent var	28.9832	30.4579	30.4548
S.D. Dependent var	0.0496	0.0972	0.0986

Note: ***, ** and * denote statistical significance of variable coefficients at 1%, 5% and 10%. Numbers in parentheses are standard errors.

Source: Authors' Computation

5.0. Conclusion

According to this study, Nigeria's technology investment is relatively low in the industrial sector and has not yielded notable outcomes. Overall, the study emphasises that technology investment is crucial for enhancing industrial outputs and economic growth, suggesting that Nigeria should increase its technology spending to promote economic expansion. Thus, this study concludes that, if adequately supported, technology investment in the industrial sector will have a growth-enhancing effect in Nigeria. Elevating technology investment at the business, sectoral, and aggregate levels is undeniably essential to maximising productivity gains and fostering economic growth in Nigeria. Therefore, to fully realise the developmental potential of technology investment, it is necessary for the government and businesses to consistently invest in technology, as well as in innovation ecosystems, particularly in the industrial sector of the Nigerian economy.

6.0. Policy Recommendations

The findings indicate that technology investment in Nigeria's industrial sector remains insufficient to drive significant economic growth. Therefore, the government should introduce tax credits for firms investing in advanced manufacturing technologies (e.g., robotics, AI). Furthermore, the establishment of a public-private technology fund to co-finance industrial R&D projects is long overdue. In addition, the government should address macroeconomic constraints to technology investment by stabilising the exchange rate fluctuations and mitigating the effects of the terms of trade on the economy through export promotion and prioritising local input production to enhance optimal outputs and economic growth in Nigeria.

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